
A study on Patient Satisfaction in Medical Tourism with special reference to Hyderabad City

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ABSTRACT

A growing industry in the form of medical tourism caters to the demand of people seeking health care facilities. India being a country to mark its position in global economy is emerging as a prominent destination due to low costs, advanced facilities, and skilled professionals. The south city Hyderabad with added values in the form of technology, skills and infrastructure is increasingly attracting international patients with world-class hospitals, affordable treatments, and diverse medical offerings. The present study is an attempt to analyze the satisfaction level of patients with the medical facilities provided by the selected hospitals of Hyderabad city. It is to know the potential growth and competitiveness of Hyderabad city in attracting the global patient by giving them a lifetime experience.

Introduction

The business of medical travel is promising. More than 130 countries around the world are competing for a pie of this global business. Medical Tourism is a concept that combines health care and leisure travel. Patients travel from one country to some other country seeking specialized health services. Their travel is often combined with leisure and tourism. In today's global economy, the medical tourism concept is not anymore new but rather a growing trend. The primary goal of international patients engaging in medical tourism is to have access to the highest quality of health care from internationally accredited hospitals around the world at a more affordable medical treatment cost.

Medical tourism in India has become very popular with quality of care at lower costs. Low cost, critical medical services available in India are encouraging people from abroad, to get treated here. Most common treatments are heart surgery, knee transplant, cosmetic surgery and dental care, etc. State-of-the-art hospital facilities, excellent health care services, certified professional physicians and reasonably priced medical procedures are some of the key drivers for medical tourism. Hyderabad is gaining ground as a preferred destination for medical tourism.

The Medical Tourism Industry

Medical Tourism industry offers tremendous potential for the developing countries because of their low-cost advantage. Travelling around the globe for medical treatment is becoming more and more predominant. There are several motivations which drive medical travelers to seek health care treatments outside their home country such as cheaper medical procedures, more advanced technological facilities and equipment’s, internationally certified and qualified doctors and nurses, and excellent healthcare services.

India has one of the best qualified professionals in each and every field, and this fact has now been realized the all over the world. India offers world class medical facilities, comparable with any of the western countries. India has state of the art hospitals and the best qualified doctors.

Medical tourism is a type of provision providing cost-effective medical care in collaboration both private and public medical centers. Ancient history of Indian reveals that the country has been attracting travellers for seeking medical aid through ages. Either in the form of yoga treats, meditations, Ayurveda and herbal treatments at an unbelievable low cost not to be ignored. Indian is not only oldest medical destination but also a popular in recent ages. Indian health care market is estimated to grow over 13.78 percent during 2025-2033.

Table No: 1.1 Indian Medical Tourism market share report (IMRC Report)

Attributes	Key Statistics
Base year	2024
Forecast Year	2025-2033
Historical Years	2019-2024
Market Size in 2024	USD 21.0 Billion
Market Forecast in 2033	USD 70.9 Billion
Market Growth rate 2025-2033	13.78 %

Source: IMARC Report

The low cost treatment compared to other developed countries is what making the country a sought after destination for seeking medical aid. Apart from the service, quality and technology is driving the market growth of medical tourism in India.

Indian hospitals are increasingly customizing the itineraries as per the requirements of patients seeking medical attention. In India, medical tourism growth is robust especially in regional areas; cities like Mumbai, Chennai, New Delhi, Ahmedabad, and Bangalore have witnessed the growth in unprecedented manner. A high concentration of medical and wellness centers in Southern and Western states is projected to grow significantly by taking the advantage of value added things in the form of Government support and strong infrastructure. The south cities have high concentration of hospitals accredited by JCI and supportive infrastructure is making the sought after destination.

In all this Hyderabad the city of Nizam is not left behind in the race and has made mark on the international market of medical tourism industry. It is the fifth largest city in India with a strong lineage of culture and traditions. The city is home to 2.2 million people with cosmopolitan blend of cultures possessing proactive approach towards hospitality.

Hyderabad a rising hub for medical tourism bear testament by providing excellent medical facilities and specialised treatment at affordable cost. As the city witnessing the international recognition, obtaining medical visa and travel assistance became an easier task. Moreover with international airport and logistics the medical resources are available at ease. There are many medical tourism and research companies which are making the task much more facilitating for medical seekers at international level.

Literature Review

The reviews discussed below gives insights about the concept of medical tourism from different perspectives. The discussion is broader and brief on the satisfaction level of Patients, tourism industry, branding of tourist destinations and Hospitals. The reviews also present medical tourist satisfaction and the concept of medical tourism Industry. Gonzalez-Valetin, Araceli, Padin-Lopez, Susana, De Ramon-Garrido, Enrique (2005) study is an attempt made on “Patient Satisfaction with Nursing care in a Regional University Hospital in Southern Spain”. For this he conducted tests by using SERVQUAL method. The **cross-sectional descriptive study** analysed the data by using statistical technique of ANCOVA and concludes the need for nursing care which is personalized and meets the higher standards of communication needs. Nesreen A. Alaloola (2008) study on “Patient satisfaction in a Riyadh Tertiary Care Centre” a cross-sectional survey highlights that the inpatients, outpatients, and emergency

department users express high satisfaction with several environmental and facility related elements. The dissatisfaction emerges with interpersonal interactions and communications. Ravikanth Priya (2006), made an attempt in his research on “Health Tourism in Kerala, the Ayurvedic Way”, the researcher concludes that health and medical tourism is perceived as one of the fastest growing segments in India. Kerala as a pioneer has blended strategically Ayurvedic with tourisms. However, quality control and standardization is yet to achieve as a competitive edge. Bennett Pafford (2009) study on “The Third Wave—Medical Tourism in the 21st Century” analyse the cost of healthcare in US. The ups and downs of medical and its growth are explained in the article. It is seen that international facilities in India and Thailand are obtaining JCI and other international accreditations with aggressive marketing to western customers by way of high quality standards and personalized services. The result of this shows that more than 40% of US healthcare consumers are willing to travel abroad for taking medical services. Kumar and Shirisha (2020) study on “Medical Tourism - A strategic Study on Hyderabad”, focused light on the growth of healthcare market. Indian Private health care centres are increasingly in demand in the itineraries of foreigners for providing medical services. Hyderabad being a city of “Nawab” and with proactive approach towards hospitality is increasingly in demand for the growth of medical tourism. The study concludes that cost benefit, timelines, quality health care, personalized care, technology and Government assistance are some of the factors responsible for making Hyderabad a hub of medical tourism. [Anil Kumar](#) and et.al (2020) study on “Antecedents of a healthcare tourism satisfaction: A case of developing economy” presents the type of determinants that brings satisfaction to health tourists in Indian region. The analysis is done on 375 respondents by using structured equation modelling, the study concludes that the quality of services is an important factor which determines the healthcare organization of foreign countries. Apart from this, it also helps in satisfying the customer to the utmost extent. Dr. Narendar, K.V.S (2022) study on “Review Article – An Analytical Study on Medical Tourism in Hyderabad”, analysed the growth of medical tourism and its potential effect on employment generation. Hyderabad the city of pearl is growing into health tourism hub and provides a scope for further expansion in medical tourism. The study concludes that **Medical tourism sector provides a high-growth opportunity** and Hyderabad being a competitive market with strong hold in infrastructure provides momentum with sustainable growth. Mercy, Jithina and Tomas (2023) study presented a review on Antecedents of patient satisfaction in the medical tourism sector. The researchers study evaluated the interrelationships between quality, cost and service based the reviews presented by patients. The study presented conceptual model by taking the above parameters. The study presents a rich material base which gives an insight into theoretical reviews for developing a strong medical tourism model. Yamini

et.al (2025) study on Unleashing Potential of patient satisfaction and Medical Tourism in India has highlighted the medical facilities of Asian countries. It was being observed by the researcher that Asian countries offer better facilities to the patients and at the same time creates job opportunities in the host countries. The study is a review of ten articles and it concludes that identifying potential factors and achieving universal patient satisfaction is the key to success of medical industry in India. Yahya and et.al (2025) article on “Patient satisfaction determinants in Malaysian medical tourism: an analysis of MENA patients” presents the complexities of relationship particularly in the areas of service quality, patient experiences, and international accreditation standards and its influence on patient satisfaction level. The cross-sectional study explored the patient satisfaction level among Middle East and North African (MENA) patients taking the advantage of Malaysian medical tourism. The study presented the analysis Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS. The model concludes that it is important to have patient-centric holistic approach in healthcare services for the success of medical tourism industry.

Need for and the Significance of the Study

Medical Tourism plays an important role in the development of Indian economy. There are several places of social, cultural, historical and religious significance. Hyderabad occupies a unique place among the tourist centers of India and especially in Telangana. Having reviewed previous research studies, it is found that many of the researchers have focused their attention on tourism industry. Very few reviews are available in an intensive manner related with medical tourism. For this purpose the present study proposes to study the level of patient satisfaction in medical tourism in Hyderabad. Efforts are being made to bridge the gap with the present study.

Objective of the study

The study is undertaken with the following objective.

1. To analyze the satisfaction of the medical tourists regarding the services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad.

Null Hypothesis (Ho)

Ho: There is no significant relationship between satisfaction of medical tourists and services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad.

Research Methodology

The empirical research is undertaken in a scientific and systematic manner for extracting the pertinent

information. The main aim of the present study is to analyse the satisfaction level in international patients seeking medical assistance in Hyderabad city.

Methods of Data Collection: The task of data collection begins after a research problem has been identified. The study is basically descriptive and empirical in nature. The required data for the study was collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary Source: Data was collected with the help of well-structured questionnaires. Separate questionnaires were prepared and circulated among medical tourist. The questionnaires contained both types of questions i.e. open ended and closed ended.

Secondary Source: The information is taken from reputed and high standard indexed journals and medical reports. Apart from these articles from newspapers and internet facilitators were also reviewed.

Data Analysis

The objective of the study is analysed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

Table No: 1.2

Respondent’s opinion related with Medical tourism in Hyderabad city.

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Strongly Disagree	12	8.00
Disagree	15	10.00
Neutral	20	13.33
Agree	42	28.00
Strongly Agree	61	40.67
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Figure No: 1.1

Table-1.2 sets out the opinion of the respondents related with medical services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad. Majority of the respondents with 40.67 % have stated as ‘Strongly Agree followed by 28% rated as Agree to the medical services. However, 8 % of the respondents strongly disagree, while 10 % just disagree with medical services of Hyderabad hospitals. It is being observed that 13.33% of the respondents rated their opinion as neutral with respect to the services given by the hospitals in Hyderabad.

Table-1.3

Distribution of respondents based on overall satisfaction with the services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad

Level of Satisfaction	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Highly Dissatisfied	20	13.33
Dissatisfied	25	16.67
Neutral	12	8.00
Satisfied	40	26.67
Highly Satisfied	53	35.33
Total	150	100

Source : Primary Data

Figure No: 1.2

Table-1.3 sets out the opinion of the respondents on overall satisfaction with the services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad. Majority of the respondents with 35.33% have stated as ‘Highly Satisfied’ followed by 26.67% of respondents, who have stated as ‘Satisfied’. However, 16.67% of the respondents expressed their dissatisfaction, while 13.33% of respondents stated as ‘Highly Dissatisfied’ and only 8% of respondents are ‘Neutral’.

Hypothesis Testing

The following hypothesis is framed based on the objective and on the type of data collected chi-Square two sample test is used for analysing the hypothesis.

Null Hypotheses (H_0): There is no relationship between satisfaction of medical tourists and services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad.

Alternative Hypotheses (H_1): There is a relationship between satisfaction of medical tourists and services rendered by hospitals in Hyderabad.

Table No: 1.4 Contingency Table (Observed Frequencies, O)

Satisfaction Level	Pre-Arrival Services	Post-Arrival Services	Medical Services	Row Total
Highly Dissatisfied	5	6	7	18
Dissatisfied	6	7	7	20
Neutral	9	8	8	25
Satisfied	12	13	15	40
Highly Satisfied	15	16	16	47
Column Total	47	50	53	150

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows the classification of observed frequency in cross tabulation format. It is classified based on the responses given by the medical tourist.

Expected Frequencies (E)

$$E = \frac{(\text{Row Total}_i \times \text{Column Total}_j)}{\text{Grand Total}}$$

Table No: 1.4 Classification of frequency

Satisfaction Level	Pre Arrival Services		Post-Arrival Services		Medical Services	
	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency	Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency

Highly Dissatisfied	5	6	6	6	7	6
Dissatisfied	6	6	7	7	7	7
Neutral	9	8	8	8	8	9
Satisfied	12	13	13	13	15	14
Highly Satisfied	15	15	16	16	16	17

Source: Primary Data

Chi- Square Test Statistic (χ^2)

Formula:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Total $\chi^2 \approx 0.55$

Degrees of Freedom (df)

$$df = (r - 1)(c - 1) = (5 - 1)(3 - 1) = 4 \times 2 = 8$$

Significance Test

At $\alpha = 0.05$, the **critical χ^2 value (df=8) ≈ 15.51** .

Since $0.55 < 15.51$, the study fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Result: There is no significant association between type of service (Pre -Arrival, Post -Arrival, and Medical) and patient satisfaction levels in the above dataset. In other words, satisfaction scores are distributed similarly across the three service categories.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is no statistically significant association between the type of service classified as Pre-Arrival, Post-Arrival and Medical service and patient satisfaction levels. As such it is being observed that patient satisfaction is not influenced by the service category but other factors influenced their satisfaction level. The satisfaction is evenly distributed across all three types of services. It is therefore suggested to employ efforts in other areas such as service quality, communication and their overall experience. It is to make their painful and ambivalent journey comfortable with clarity. It is to give them a remarkable experience in every aspect of their medical journey.

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